

SCHWEIZER JUGEND FORSCHT
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The influence of the habitat on the presence of amphibians (Val Müstair, GR)

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Abstract

The quality of the habitat plays an essential role in the presence of amphibians. However, the good conditions of living are not every time reunited. In addition, the amphibians are one of the most threatened vertebrates.

This study took place into Val Müstair during July 2020. 21 ponds have been investigated and an inventory has been made. It includes data concerning the amphibian's population and species such as the common frog (*Rana temporaria*) and the alpine newt (*Ichthyosaura alpestris*) as well as a classification of the pond's quality. Therefore, different categories were chosen: surroundings, plants, sunshine, water level, water soil, sealing, altitude.

The results show that there are more amphibians in sunny ponds or semi-shade (changing) ponds. It is furthermore demonstrated that these two amphibian's species do not bound to prefer the same places since most ponds in the main valley are dominated by the common frog whereas ponds in higher altitudes are preferred by the alpine newt. In summary, there are several ponds that need a management plan to improve the living conditions for amphibians. Additionally, the effect of fish in a pond on the presence of amphibians is discussed.

Finally, some solutions have been proposed to improve the conditions of living of the amphibians in Val Müstair.

1. Introduction

The amphibians are vertebrates and they can be separated in three classes: Anura, Urodela and Apoda. Around the world approximately 7000 different species exist. However, at this point in time, there have only 20 species been detected in Switzerland. Out of which only two, the common frog (*Rana temporaria*) and the alpine newt (*Ichthyosaura alpestris*) are known to be living in the Val Müstair. Both species are shown in the pictures below (Picture 1 Picture 2)

Picture 1: Common Frog (*Rana temporaria*)

Picture 2: Alpine Newt (*Ichthyosaura alpestris*)

The common frog is the most widespread frog in Europe and Switzerland because of its ability to live in rude conditions, for example in a wide range of altitudes. E.g. common frog has been found in a height of 2'750 meters (Karch, 2000). The alpine newt can be found in lowland ponds as well as in high altitude ponds (2300m above sea-level) and has a size from 8cm to 10cm. The male is more colored than the female but the latter is bigger.

Their larvae are very distinctive because the one of the newts have legs and arms as well their gills outside the head on the contrary to the frogs' larvae.

In general, the development of amphibians occurs in a two-phase cycle. In the beginning, the eggs hatch and give way to larvae. For example, the alpine newts wrap their eggs one by one into leaves. After about 1- 1.5 months, as the development goes on, the legs and arms grow. After another few days the metamorphosis (the so-called conversion to a land-living animal) takes place. The sustenance for amphibians is made up of little preys that cannot move too fast like small insects, spiders, worms, slugs, snails etc.

Because of the amphibian`s poikilothermy and their frost sensitivity they have to undergo hibernation in a cold avoided place (either on land or in water, so called wintering place). As most hibernation places are outside the pond migration is triggered in spring and autumn for adults as well as in summer for the offspring. Mortality rates of amphibians are inter alia explained by decaying plant standing in the ponds as well as highway traffic. "In fact, they are considered the most endangered class of vertebrates." (Kyek et al.,2017)

It is therefore inevitable to have a picture of the entire habitat of the amphibians and not only the ponds itself.

The Val Müstair and its surrounding alpine area are rich in both biodiversity and different kinds of habitats. Because of the extraordinary nature objects, landscape and the cultural heritages found in the valley of Müstair, it belongs to the regional nature park of national importance called Biosfera Val Müstair. Some ponds within this perimeter belong to the *Bundesinventar der Amphibienlaichgebiete von nationaler Bedeutung* (IANB) meaning this is an area of

national importance among other means for the reproduction of the amphibians. There are about 19 spawning areas known in Val Müstair of which five belong to the IANB (BAFU, 2020). The ponds can be found at different altitudes.

As there is only few data existing about the habitat of amphibians in the valley of Müstair the researchers focused in this qualitative research on the following question:

How does the location and quality of the habitat especially in terms of sunshine, plants and surroundings in the Val Müstair (GR) affect the presence of the amphibians?

2. Material & Methods

The field work of the performed data acquisition was based on creating an inventory of the ponds according to the *National Coordination Office for Amphibians and Reptiles Protection in Switzerland* (KARCH) guidelines and took place on the 20th, 21th, 22th of July 2020 in the valley of Müstair, the canton of Graubünden, Switzerland. Within the KARCH guidelines data concerning the spawning ground (protection, maintenance and design measures, dangers and its causes as well as the change of state), the spawning waters (main type, surroundings and uses, coordinates, sealing, plants, water soil, water level, water quality and sunshine) as well the existing amphibians (*Rana temporaria* and *Ichthyosaura alpestris* (nomenclature after CSCF-karch)) was documented by walking around the ponds and using the following materials: KARCH guidelines, writing material, binoculars, camera: Sony RX10, fishing net and a closed cup.

21 ponds are classified as a spawning area in the Val Müstair. Initially 16 known ponds were chosen out of two maps (Inventare Naturschutz by Conservation department of Graubünden; KARCH). Five ponds were classified additionally during field work which are neither registered in the KARCH or the Conservation department of Graubünden (Val Vau, Tea Fondada, Lai da Zoppà, Donkey pond and Rocky Pond).

To be sure to do the research respectfully and to not hurt the animals, the researchers mainly used binoculars to count and classify the amphibians.

In the end all data has been analyzed, classified and presented for this report.

In the following table, the different ponds are numbered, their coordinates, the altitude, actual pond size and the protection status are listed:

Number	Name	Coordinates	Altitude	Size	Protection
1	Schler Dal Podestà	46°37'26" N / 10°27'14" E	1248 m.	980m ²	Yes
2	Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder	46°36'22" N / 10°25'27" E	1338m.	1176m ²	Yes
3	Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder	46°36'24" N / 10°25'29" E	1338m.	605m ²	Yes
4	Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder	46°36'25" N / 10°25'31" E	1338m.	431m ²	Yes
5	Fuldera d'Aint (Punt planet)	46°36'55" N / 10°22'07" E	1615m.	330m ²	Yes
6	Fuldera d'Aint (Punt planet)	46°36'53" N / 10°22'09" E	1615m.	120m ²	Yes
7	Stalia (Stretta)	46°37'36" N / 10°20'21" E	1665m.	139m ²	No

8	Palüsura	46°37'26" N / 10°19'38" E	1785m.	2381m ²	No
9	Tea Fondada	46°34'33" N / 10°19'07" E	2139m.	411m ²	No
10	Val Vau	46°35'29" N / 10°24'06" E	1695m.	68m ²	No
11	Val Vau	46°35'29" N / 10°24'06" E	1694m.	17m ²	No
12	Val Vau	46°35'29" N / 10°24'06" E	1694m.	33m ²	No
13	Plazzaraun	46°36'05" N / 10°23'25" E	1558m.	656m ²	Yes
14	Donkey pond	46°37'04" N / 10°21'09" E	1635m.	165m ²	No
15	Palüds Cotschnas	46°36'40" N / 10°21'37" E	1625m.	547m ²	No
16	Lai Da Valpaschun	46°37'10" N / 10°23'59" E	2170m.	622m ²	Yes
17	Lai Da Valpaschun	46°37'09" N / 10°24'01" E	2167m.	208m ²	Yes
18	Rocky pond	46°36'36" N / 10°20'43" E	1963m.	206m ²	No
19	Lai Zoppa	46°36'37" N / 10°20'28" E	2009m.	614m ²	No
20	Lai da Juata	46°38'15" N / 10°20'39" E	2229m.	1861m ²	Yes
21	Las Vals	46°38'15" N / 10°20'18" E	2247m.	148m ²	No

Table 1: Overview of observed ponds (numbers, names, coordinates, altitudes, sizes and protection status)

The following map shows the different sampling sites in red as well as the regional fen areas marked in green:

Figure 1: Overview of the studied ponds. Since the spawning area 2-4, 5-6 and 10-12 count several ponds, there presented in more detail in Appendix.

3. Results

Overview:

In the 21 ponds 7007 individuals are detected out of which 89.87% (6297 individuals) belong to the common grass frog and the remaining 10.13% (710 individuals) are defined as alpine newts.

Whereas 42 adults, 1908 juveniles, 4347 larvae are counted of the common frog the corresponding numbers for the alpine newts are as followed: 124 male adults, 53 female adults, 35 unknown adults, 51 juveniles and 447 larvae.

Water quality:

99.54% of the found amphibians live in a habitat with good water quality and for 0.46% of the amphibians the habitat is eutrophicated.

Main pond types:

By means of this research two main types of ponds can be characterized in the valley Müstair: Ponds with and ponds without flow. But as it can be read the presence of amphibians does not or only slightly differ in the different main types (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of main type of pond on the presence of amphibians

Fish:

When looking on the presence of fish the focus is on the minnow (*Phoxinus phoxinus*). In one pond at Santa Maria Plaun Schumpeder there also occur trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). It can be stated that in 28.57% of the ponds (6 ponds, Figure 3) fish are present.

Figure 3: Distribution of fish in the ponds (three sampling sites having fish, in total six ponds have fish)

Whereas no alpine newt is found in ponds with fish, overall nine adult common frogs were found in ponds with fish. A surprising case is the pond Plazzaraum since about 1000 juveniles and 2000 larvae are counted in a pond with small minnow. It is furthermore important to note that in some ponds there is explicitly bait fish exposed such as in the three ponds in Santa Maria Plaun Schumpeder (Numbers 2-4).

In the ponds where no fish is present 37 adult common frogs, 907 juvenile common frogs and 2345 common frogs are counted as well as 209 adult alpine newts, 51 juvenile alpine newts and 447 alpine newt larvae.

Sunshine:

With regards to the sunshine in a habitat it can be said that the common frogs and alpine newts are encountered in sunny or changing ponds (Picture 3). Whereas a preference of the common frog in sunny ponds is noted the highest value of alpine newts is accounted in changing ponds. In umbrageous places (Picture 4) neither alpine newt larvae nor common frog live.

Picture 4: Example of an umbrageous pond

Picture 3: Example of a sunny pond

Surroundings:

When focusing on the surroundings of the ponds it can be seen that the highest numbers of juvenile and the larvae of the common frog is firstly in meadow surrounding and secondly in alp surrounding (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of common frogs in natural surroundings. (Since there were two outliers of the larvae and juveniles of the common frog they are presented separately in Table 2 in order to keep a good visualization.)

The same distribution can be seen for the alpine newt. Additionally, one has to be taken note of the one adult common frog and the one female alpine newt found in the Lai Zoppa where no amphibians have been registered yet.

It is furthermore discernible that the common frog was found in the natural surroundings with a majority of larvae and few larvae of alpine newts.

As it can be read from the corresponding diagram the larvae of common frogs were very present in the forest surroundings. The adult frogs were also present but less than the larvae whereas the alpine newt has not been found at all.

When observing ponds around a meadow only adult common frog were found as well as alpine newts.

In the fen surrounding no alpine newt has been seen. However, the presence of common frogs has been noted, distributed equally between adults and juveniles.

In the rockfall surrounding, too; namely one adult common frog and one adult alpine newt.

Where the pond bordered on an alp surrounding alpine newts can be found whereas the larvae outweigh the adults. Adults and juveniles of the common frogs have been encountered, too.

Furthermore, one has to denote that the surrounding of one pond (rocky pond) could not have been specified. In this pond three adult common frogs were found but no juvenile and no larvae.

The corresponding graphs can be seen in the appendix.

Plants:

With regards to the plants it has to be differentiated between underwater plants, floating plants and reeds.

Concerning the relation of floating plants, the respective distribution of no major impact can be denoted (see appendix). Also, the presence of amphibians independently on the distribution of reeds remains very low. Whereas the larvae of the common frog make up the greatest number when the pond is partially covered with reeds (Figure 5) and their adults account for the biggest number in a fully reed covered pond.

Figure 5: Presence of common frog with partially reeds. (Since there were two outliers of the larvae and juveniles of the common frog they are presented separately in Table 2 in order to keep a good visualization.)

Altitude:

The distribution of individuals in function of the height demonstrates that in lower altitudes only common frogs are present. The presence of two alpine newts is firstly seen at 1635 meters above sea-level in the donkey pond. In the three highest ponds (2170 meter above sea-level to 2247 meters above sea-level) alpine newts individuals have been encountered without exception (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Number of individuals per pond in function of the altitude (starting with the lowest pond on the lefthand side)

4. Discussion

In this chapter the results outlined in the previous chapter are analysed more in depth and final conclusions are drawn.

Sunshine:

No larvae were found in the sunny ponds despite the fact that they “like” warm water which can be seen as an indication that the larvae already left the ponds one hand due to fact the data acquisition took place in July and other hand due to the very high and unusual temperatures during the field work.

Fish:

The common minnow is an omnivore and a generalist which makes it a predatory species in many habitats. It is known from several studies that the presence of fish endangers the population of amphibians and thus the cohabitee of fish and amphibians does is not expect to function. The common minnow is possibly a better predator in general as well as sometimes tadpoles get eaten. This hypothesis can among other means be supported by the findings of this study as in all the ponds where either adult fish and/or a larger population of fish has been detected none or only a few common grass frogs were found. Furthermore, it is important to note that bait fish has been found in ponds of national importance (e.g. in ponds of Fuldera d' Aint). But as the coexistence of fish and amphibians is regarded as critical this barley contributes to protect the amphibians in the ponds of national importance. Therefore, it is to be analysed more in depth and reach an agreement on how one wants to protect the amphibians in the national ponds of importance (e.g. by more frequent controls and effective measures, by drying out the ponds to remove the fish). This analysis is in particular advised on ponds where the bait fish is still very small inter alia pond Plazzaraum.

Altitude:

The collected data regarding the altitude suggests that the alpine newts prefer higher altitudes. However, this cannot be supported to a 100% as no evidence has been found in expert literature that this is applicable. In return, the more frequent distribution in higher altitudes might be rather explained with the steadily decreasing temperatures with raising height and the therefore connected time lag in development.

Plants:

When looking at the graphs presenting the connection of underwater plants and the distribution of amphibians the most striking aspect is that the adults of the alpine newt are the mostly present if there are no underwater plants whereas their registered larvae can be found in ponds with fully covered underwater plants.

Despite the meadows being the surrounding with the most found amphibians it should be stated that especially those ponds are endangered to be overfertilized in the in a long-term time span. Resulting of this fact it is important to keep an eye on those meadows in order to avoid such an effect which would raise the percentages of eutrophicated ponds. To stop any further overfertilization an immediate stop of using fertilizers at all is suggested.

At the same time the researchers are aware of the fact that this proposed solution is likely to contradict with the winning strategy of the local farmers in the valley Müstair. Therefore, taking the following measures are suggested: using sustainable dung, keeping the cattle in a preferable distance to the pond and raising awareness of the issue among farmers as well as among the local people of the Val Müstair.

In fact, eutrophication in so called “perfect places” such as the Val Vau is from an amphibian protective point of view not endeavoured. This is among other means of high importance as the amphibians are seen as the most endangered vertebrates across the world due to their habitat loss. For example, even in the Val Müstair habitat loss is happening: The IANB Plaun Schumpeder is inexistent since a horse barn is standing at its place.

Another point connected to this problematic is that the meadows become fattier due to which reduces the plant and biodiversity and has a negative reaction of links. This negative reaction of links has on one hand an indirect effect on the habitat of amphibians and is on the other hand connected to climate change and its self-enforcing effects. It is therefore essential to follow a sustainable maintenance

Wider-context:

In fact, Val Müstair is located at a very interesting height in which changing factors such as the impact of the raising temperature due to climate change are denoted in a more sensitively. It cannot be negotiated that the amphibians will have to adapt to the changes caused by climate change. However, one has to be seen that climate change might threaten the basic tools of living for amphibians (e.g. migration starts when the first snow has melted and the tadpoles which already have migrated to the ponds freeze). Another unfortunate scenario is the non-appearance of snow which leads to the fact that the hibernation will be disturbed.

Further research:

The analysing of the migration routes of amphibians is a section in which further research is recommended.

Another point which has to be clarified is the establishment of a fence around the ponds such as Lai da Valpaschun. Nevertheless, one has to be aware that only fence in the ponds might protect them from the cattle but not form hikers who wish to enter the pond. With regards to the latter stated point the responsible authorities are demanded to come up with a concept involving arraying respective signs in order to sensitize the people.

Conclusion:

As it can be deduced from chapters three and four as well from expert literature the habitat of an amphibian is always determined by several factors. Thereof it can be further concluded that also the presence of amphibians is determined by several factors and not a single one. Within the frame of this study the researchers only were able to draw a bigger picture of some factors. However, they are aware that further research is needed to state whether and if one factor of the habitat influences the presence of amphibians most.

5. Acknowledgements

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7. Appendix

a) Overview of the ponds which were to close:

Figure 7 : Overview of the ponds number 2, 3 and 4 (Santa Maria)

Figure 8 : Overview of the ponds number 10, 11 and 12 (Val Vau)

Figure 9 : Overview of the ponds number 5 and 6 (Fuldera d'Aint)

Figure 10 : Overview of the ponds number 16 and 17

b) Pictures of every pond

Figure 11 : Schler Dal Podestà (1)

Figure 12 :Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder (2)

Figure 13 : Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder (3)

Figure 14 : Santa Maria Plaum Schumpeder (4)

Figure 15 : : Fuldera d'Aint (5)

Figure 16 : Fuldera d'Aint (6)

Figure 17 : Stalia (7)

Figure 18 : Palüsura (8)

Figure 19 : Tea Fondada (9)

Figure 20 : Val Vau (10)

Figure 21 : Val Vau (11)

Figure 22 : Val Vau (12)

Figure 23 : Plazzaraun (13)

Figure 24 : Donkey pond (14)

Figure 25 : Palüds Cotschnas (15)

Figure 26 : Lai Da Valpaschun (16)

Figure 27 : Lai Da Valpaschun (17)

Figure 28 : Rocky pond (18)

Figure 29 : Lai Zoppa (19)

Figure 30 : Lai da Juata (20)

Figure 31 : Las Val (21)

c) Diagrams

Table 2: Outliers

Number of pond	name of pond	Altitude	Size	RaTe_ADU	RaTE_juv	RaTE_larv	IcAI_ADU	IcAI_larv
13	Plazzaraun	1558m.	656m ²	0	1000	2000	0	0
20	Lai da Juata	2229m.	1861m ²	17	900	2200	28	0

On the left-hand side always the figures of the common frogs can be found in which the values of the outliers in Table 2: Outliers have been purposefully taken out in order to keep a good visualization in which trends can be seen.

Figure 32 : Distribution of common frogs in rockfall surroundings

Figure 33 : Distribution of alpine newts in rockfall surroundings

Figure 34 : Distribution of common frogs in forest surroundings

Figure 35 : Distribution of alpine newts in forest surroundings

Figure 36 : Distribution of common frogs in natural surroundings

Figure 37 : Distribution of alpine newts in natural surroundings

Figure 38 : Distribution of common frogs in alp surroundings

Figure 39 : Distribution of alpine newts in alp surroundings

Figure 40 : Distribution of common frogs in meadow surroundings

Figure 41 : Distribution of alpine newts in meadow surroundings

Figure 42 : Distribution of common frogs in fen surroundings

Figure 43 : Distribution of alpine newts in fen surroundings

Figure 44 . Distribution of common frogs in unknown surroundings

Figure 45 : Distribution of common frogs in unknown surroundings

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 SCIENCE ET JEUNESSE
 SCIENZA E GIOVENTÙ
 Presence of common frog with no reeds

Figure 46 : Presence of common frog with no reeds

Presence of alpine newt with no reeds

Figure 47 : Presence of alpine newts with no reeds

Presence of common frog with single reeds

Figure 48 : Presence of common frog with single reeds

Presence of alpine newt with single reeds

Figure 49 : Presence of alpine newt with single reeds

Presence of common frog with partially reeds

Figure 50 : Presence of common frog with partially reeds

Presence of alpine newt partially covered with reeds

Figure 51 : Presence of alpine newt with partially reeds

Presence of common frog with fully covered reeds

Figure 52 : Presence of common frog with fully covered reeds

Presence of alpine newt fully covered with reeds

Figure 53 : Presence of alpine newt with fully covered reeds

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 SCIENCE ET JEUNESSE
 SCIENZA E GIOVENTÙ

Figure 54 : presence of common frog with no floating plants

Figure 55 : presence of alpine newt with no floating plants

Figure 56 : presence of common frog with single floating plants

Figure 57 : presence of alpine newt with single floating plants

Figure 58 : presence of common frog with partially floating plants

Figure 59 : presence of alpine newt with partially floating plants

Figure 60 : presence of common frog with no underwater plants

Figure 61 : presence of alpine newt with no underwater plants

SCHWEIZER JUGEND FORSCHT
SCIENCE ET JEUNESSE
SCIENZA E GIOVENTÙ

Presence of common s frog with single underwater plants

Figure 62 : presence of common frog with single underwater plants

Figure 64 : presence of common frog with partial underwater plants

Figure 66 : presence of common frog with fully covered underwater plants

Figure 68 : Presence of common frog in sunny ponds

Presence of alpine newt with single underwater plants

Figure 63 : presence of alpine newt with single underwater plants

Presence of alpine newt with partialy underwater plants

Figure 65 : presence of alpine newt with partial underwater plants

Presence of alpine newt with fully covered underwaterplants

Figure 67 : presence of alpine newt with fully covered underwater plants

Presence of alpine newts in sunny ponds

Figure 69 : Presence of alpine newt in sunny ponds

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 SCIENCE ET JEUNESSE
 SCIENZA E GIOVENTÙ

Figure 70 : Presence of common frog in changing ponds

Figure 71 : Presence of alpine newt in changing ponds

Figure 72 : Presence of common frog in umbrageous ponds

Figure 73 : Presence of alpine newt in umbrageous ponds